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**UTILIZATION AND INTEGRATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION
TECHNOLOGY IN THE SCHOOL SYSTEM: THE CASE AMONG THE SECONDARY
SCHOOLS IN LEYTE DIVISION**

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ABSTRACT

The main objective of this study aimed to determine the utilization and integration of information and communication technology in the school system among the secondary schools in Leyte Division during the school year 2010-2015. This study utilized the descriptive design which is appropriate to the questionnaire made as instrument for data gathering.

The profile of the Department of Education Computerization Program is a major asset which became the core strength in its implementation since the respondents possessed the qualifications needed for them to implement, manage and operationalize the program, although in some aspects deficiencies was still present.

The program components were on the average in terms of utilization as well as implementation. Conspicuously, it was implemented partially in that sense.

Utilization of ICT resources is not equitable and it requires procedural and workable measures to improve implementation. Interestingly, monitoring and evaluation is carefully observed and therefore highly implemented. This should be sustained so utilization would be fully integrated in the education system.

Some of the strategies were highly implemented and only in few areas that implementation was in the average level.

The perceptions of the school administrators, ICT coordinators and teachers regarding the implementation of the program were in unison and that the implementation is still partial and in the average level.

The schools through the leadership and initiative of school administrators should craft out mechanisms and interventions to effectively and efficiently utilize ICT technology and fully integrate it in the education system.

KEYWORDS: Utilization, integration, information and communication technology, Department of Education Computerization Program.

INTRODUCTION

The worldwide integration of information and communication technology (ICT) into education has advanced significantly over the last two decades. People have always tried to use technology to meet their needs (Ministry of Education, 1995), and today new technologies appear almost daily. Educators, community, government and local authorities all place great importance on integrating ICT advances into education (Harrison, 2005). Much of the discussion concentrates on upgrading resources, rather than meaningfully integrating ICT in classrooms.

The use of ICT has become more common during the last two decades with the existence of the Internet and the World Wide Web. The Internet is fast becoming the largest collection of information in the world. Importantly, teachers can use the Internet to enhance teaching and learning, but this strategy needs to be well structured and sequenced (Pachler,

1999). Pachler suggested that pupils need to be prepared well for using the Internet. They need to be clear about intended learning outcomes and have clearly differentiated tasks to work on. Accordingly, students can develop as highly motivated and successful learners, provided that schools do not implement ICT superficially with existing classroom curricula and pedagogies, using it to make their schools appear modern without ensuring the efficacy of its usage.

Finger et al. (2007) stated that the term ICT is usually used to refer to computer-based and computer-related devices. However it also includes a variety of other devices that can be used for information and communication purposes. They describe ICT as a range of new devices such as the internet, mobile phones, digital cameras, plasma screens, digital video recorders, interactive whiteboards, and wireless technologies and networking. This approach enables me to consider a wide range of new technologies rather than to simply concentrate on the personal computer. Finger et al. (2007) observed that for more than two decades, ICT and education strategies have been essentially built around the personal computer tool, but that rapid change in the nature of ICT has expanded the use of ICT tools.

With the legal mandate of promoting the right of all citizens to take appropriate steps in making education accessible to all, the Department of Education (DepEd) is geared towards the transformation of education through the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP).

As stated in DepEd Order No. 78, series of 2010, DCP aims to provide public schools with appropriate technologies that would enhance the teacher-learning process and meet the challenges of the 21st Century. This program is in response to the computer backlog of public schools by providing them hardware and software, training on simple trouble shooting.

On October 2010, The Division of Leyte started the implementation of the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) – a program that provides ICT infrastructures to both secondary and elementary schools. Researches generally collect data on inputs such as teachers, students, classrooms, and expenditures. The substantive issues on program implementation and evaluation were ignored.

According to Durlak (2013), evaluations too often focus solely on program outcomes without considering how the program and its components actually produced the observed results. In other words, understanding is gained regarding what happened as a result of the program without a clear picture of how it happened. This approach can lead to inaccurate claims about how program actually produced its observed outcomes (Chen, 2008).

The challenge of the Department in realizing this vision is to be fully embraced by the Division of Leyte and share with the goals of DepEd ICT4E Strategic Plan (2008) to completely integrate ICT into the curriculum, which includes the development of multimedia instructional materials, and ICT enabled assessment. To intensify competency based professional development programs, it must establish the necessary ICT infrastructure and applications and develop processes and systems that ensure efficient, transparent and effective governance.

A national survey conducted by the New Educational Technologies (NET) Foundation in 1996 showed increases in ICT diffusion and changes in utilization. At the elementary level, about one-third of public and private schools surveyed offered computer education as a separate course (37). Fifty percent (50%) of public schools and 21% of private schools used computers as an instructional “component” of an existing subject area. The term “component” was not qualified. Among high schools, about one-half of the schools surveyed offered computer education as a separate subject, while 47% of public schools and 13% of private schools used ICT as part of another subject.

Understanding whether or not a program was implemented correctly allows implementers to more accurately interpret the relationship between the program and observed outcomes (Durlak, 2008). Implementation researches help accurately describe the program component and their associated degree of program integrity, thus fostering more accurate replication of the intervention. Without a clear understanding of these issues, difficulties can arise when replicating previously successful programs because practitioners lack information regarding how best to implement the program and the degree of integrity needed to produce observed outcomes (Domitrovich & Greenberg, 2000).

When implementation data is collected it allows researchers to more accurately determine the components of the program responsible for observed changes. Assessing implementation increases the quality of evaluation findings because it provides insights into how programs work and why they succeed or fail, rather than just focusing on outcomes (Chen, 1998).

In order to evaluate the Department of Education program implementation in the Leyte Division, educators and other stakeholders need to develop an in-depth understanding of the program. Potter Watts, and Preslar (2002) suggest that in order to increase validity of outcome findings, better picture of how program is implemented is needed because, greater understanding of program outcomes, there will be n improved dissemination of best practices, more opportunities for making informed program improvements, and effective implementation evaluation. It will give a clear understanding of what a program is supposed to accomplish and how it should be into practice.

With the abovementioned scenario, it is both timely and relevant that the Philippine government's efforts to address the underlying problems in the education system through the adoption of ICT be evaluated in order to find out whether or not such program is effective and efficient. Such is the motivation and interest of the researcher to evaluate the DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) implementation in the Division of Leyte.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study utilized the descriptive-correlational design which is appropriate to the questionnaire made as instrument for data gathering. Since the study involved variables best identified and given salient meanings purely through descriptions, the design fits the intended goal to which the researcher wanted to achieve as presented in the objectives.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in Leyte Division in Region VIII with 22 secondary schools are represented. All of these schools were DepEd Computerization Program (DCP) recipients. Specifically, school batches 9 and 25 are the target schools to be assessed.

Research Subject

The study covered only batches 9 and 25 with a total of 22 secondary schools who are recipients of the DepEd Computerization Program. 110 teachers, 22 ICT coordinators and 22 school heads shall be taken as respondents. One school head, one ICT coordinator and 5 teachers per recipient school were chosen to comprise 7 respondents from each school. Non probability sampling technique shall be used with a purpose to select those teachers who were trained and who have background information of the program.

Research Instrument

The research instrument used in this study was patterned from Engr. Dexter Enage. This was crafted through the guidelines set on DepEd Computerization Program, DCP Orientation Handbook, National Competency-Based Standards – Teachers' Strengths and Needs Assessment (NCBTS – TSNA) and National Competency-Based Standard for School Heads (NCBSSH). Three sets of questionnaires were used separately for the teachers, ICT coordinators and school heads.

The questionnaire for the teachers constitutes the socio-demographic profile such as the age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, specialization, number of years working related to ICT and seminars/trainings attended related to ICT; integration of ICT in the school system; and utilization of ICT resources.

The questionnaire for ICT coordinators comprises the socio-demographic profile such as the age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, specialization, number of years working related to ICT and seminars/trainings attended related to ICT; integration of ICT in the school system and utilization of ICT resources.

The questionnaire for school administrators is composed of the socio-demographic profile which includes age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, specialization and seminars/trainings attended related to ICT; integration of ICT in the school system and utilization of ICT resources.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researcher strictly observed and carefully followed the necessary set of procedures and processes before the actual data gathering take place. She asked permission through a letter of endorsement from the Dean of the Graduate School to the Schools Division Superintendent for approval.

Upon approval of the request, the researcher conducted the survey and facilitated the distribution of questionnaires.

The permit was shown to the school administrators of the respondent-schools to get their consent to serve as respondents of the study. The survey questionnaires were distributed and retrieved in due time.

The distribution, administration, and retrieval of the questionnaires from school administrators and teachers as well as the interviews were personally done by the researcher to ensure research protocol had been precisely observed.

Data Scoring

The data collected were organized in categories and given appropriate descriptions and interpretations using standard value ratings and levelling.

To categorize the results of the data, the following tabulation and description were used.

For strategies employed by DepED to achieve the Computerization program objectives, the following scale was used.

Mean Range	Weight	Qualitative Description
4.3 - 5.0	5	Always Utilized
3.6 - 4.2	4	Often Utilized
2.7 - 3.5	3	Frequently Utilized
1.9 - 2.6	2	Seldom Utilized
1.0 - 1.8	1	Never Utilized

For the level of implementation of the DepEd Computerization Program, the following scale was used.

Mean Range	Weight	Qualitative Description
4.3 - 5.0	5	Very Highly Implemented
3.6 - 4.2	4	Highly Implemented
2.7 - 3.5	3	Moderately Implemented
1.9 - 2.6	2	Slightly Implemented
1.0 - 1.8	1	Not Implemented

Statistical Treatment of Data

Data was coded, analyzed and tabulated with the aid of Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS).

Descriptive statistics such as range, mean and percentage were used to describe the data and tables.

Correlation analysis was utilized to find out the significant difference of the perceived implementation between the ICT coordinators and school administrators.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Profile of the Department of Education Computerization Program

This part discusses the profile of the implementers and beneficiaries of the program who are also the three sets of respondents: school administrators, ICT coordinators and ICT teachers.

School administrators. The profile of the school administrators is composed of their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, specialization, and seminars/trainings attended related to ICT. Data are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Profile of the School Administrators

Age	f	%
60 and above (senior citizen)	3	13.5
46-59 (old age)	15	68.2
22-45 (middle-aged)	4	18.2
21 and below (young)	0	0
Total	22	100.00
Sex		
Male	7	31.8
Female	15	68.2
Total	22	100.00
Civil Status		
Single	1	4.5
Married	21	95.5
Total	22	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	f	%
Doctorate Degree Holder	5	22.7
Masters Degree with Doctoral Units	5	22.7
Masters Degree Holder	10	45.5
BS Degree with Masteral Units	2	9
Total	22	100.00
Specialization	f	%
Educational Management	12	54.5
Mathematics	4	18.2
Science	2	9.1
MAPEH	1	4.5
Social Science	1	4.5
English	1	4.5
Education and Extension	1	4.5
Total	22	100.00
Local Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	5	22.7
1-3 times	16	72.7
none	1	4.5
Total	22	100.00
Regional Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	1	4.5
1-3 times	9	40.9
none	12	54.5
Total	22	100.00
National Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	0	0
1-3 times	4	18.2
none	14	81.8
Total	22	100.00

International Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	0	0
1-3 times	0	0
none	22	100.0
Total	22	100.00

It can be gleaned in table 1 that, according to age, most of the respondents at the age of 46-59 with a frequency of 15 (68.2 %) are old-age. Middle age and senior citizens were lesser with frequencies of 4 (18.2%) and 3 (13.5%) respectively. None of them is young. Since a greater number of the school administrators are within the old age bracket they are expected, as implied by the given data, to be more mature and experienced in their administrative functions.

When it comes to sex, female school administrators at the frequency of 15 (68.2%) outnumbered their male counterparts with only 7 (31.8%). Clearly, sex is not a determinant as to who reigns in the world of leadership. Likewise, it implies that men and women are now equal in the realm of leadership.

For civil status, more than ninety-percent of the school administrators at a frequency of 21 (95.5%) are married while only one (4.5%) is single. The married prevailed over the single ones which is expected since most of the school administrators are old-age.

As to highest educational attainment, nearly half of the school administrators with a frequency of 10 (45.5%) are master's degree holders and they are followed by those with master's degrees having also doctoral units and with doctoral degrees at frequencies of 5 (22.7%) each. The least are those with BS degrees with Master's units at a frequency of 2 (9%). The data suggest that the school administrators, in terms of educational attainment, are qualified. Further, it may also imply that there is still enough room for advancing their academic or educational qualifications since only few have had doctoral degrees.

For specialization, more than half with a frequency of 12 (54.5%) specialized in Educational Management, which is followed by those with a frequency of 4 (18.2%) who specialized in Mathematics. The rest, which is the least, were in other fields or disciplines. Since nearly half of the school administrators did not hold specializations in the field of management, the system of hiring and appointment of school administrators in Leyte Division does not solely rely on specialization as one of the factors/bases for such position.

As regard their trainings, a greater number of the trainings attended by the school administrators were only at the local and regional levels. There were only few times in the national level and there was none in the international level. Their training exposures appear to be less or limited and this would imply that school administrators may need upgrading and enhancement of their leadership skills and competence to cope with the changing times.

ICT coordinators. The profile of the ICT coordinators is composed of their age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, specialization, number of years working related to ICT and seminars/trainings attended related to ICT. Data are shown in Table 2.

Table 2 Profile of the ICT Coordinators

Age	f	%
60 and above (senior citizen)	0	0
46-59 (old age)	4	18.2
22-45 (middle-age)	18	81.8
21 and below (young)	0	0
Total	22	100.00
Sex	f	%
Male	13	59.1
Female	9	40.9

Total	22	100.00
Civil Status	f	%
Single	4	18.2
Married	18	81.8
Total	110	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	f	%
Doctorate Degree Holder	1	4.5
Masters Degree with Doctoral Units	1	4.5
Masters Degree Holder	9	40.9
BS Degree with Masteral Units	9	40.9
BS Degree Holder	2	9.1
Total	22	100.00
Specialization	f	%
Educational Management	2	9.1
Mathematics	6	27.3
Science	4	18.2
Biological Science	2	9.1
Social Science	1	4.5
English	3	13.6
ICT	2	9.1
Fish Culture	1	4.5
None	1	4.5
Total	22	100.00
No. of Years working related to ICT	f	%
10 years and above	6	27.3
6 to 9 years	3	13.6
2 to 5 years	10	45.5
1 year and below	3	13.6
Total	22	100.00
Local Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	4	18.2
1-3 times	13	59.1
none	5	22.7
Total	22	100.00
Regional Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	2	9.1
1-3 times	11	50.0
none	9	40.9
Total	22	100.00
National Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	0	0
1-3 times	4	18.2
none	18	81.8
Total	22	100.00
International Trainings	f	%

10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	0	0
1-3 times	0	0
none	22	100.0
Total	22	100.00

As provided in Table 2, the age reveals that majority of the ICT coordinators at the age bracket 22-45 with a frequency of 18 (81.8%) are middle-age while the remaining frequency of 4 (18.2%) at the age bracket 46-59 are old-age. This may imply that the younger ones are more oriented with and inclined to technology.

In terms of sex, the male with a frequency of 13 (59.1%) dominated the female with a frequency of 9 (40.9%). There is only a small gap between these sexes which implies that both are in equal footing when it comes to ICT.

When it comes to civil status, married ICT coordinators with a frequency of 18 (81.8%) prevailed over the single ones with a frequency of 4 (18.2%). Generally, this is expected since they are usually at marrying ages.

As to highest educational attainment, the respondents with BS degree with Master's units and the other set with Master's degrees topped with frequencies of 9 each (40.9%). This is followed by two respondents (9.1%) with BS degrees and the least is one (4.5%) with Master's degree with doctoral units and another one (4.5%) with a Doctorate degree. From the given data, implication can be drawn that the ICT coordinators have better academic qualifications.

For their specialization, the greater number of ICT coordinators with a frequency of 6 (27.3%) specialized in Mathematics and this is closely followed by those who specialized in Science with a frequency of 4 (18.2%) and English with a frequency of 3 (13.6%). The rest which is lesser in number were in other fields or disciplines, including ICT. The data would mean that becoming an ICT coordinator does not necessarily mean that you have to be ICT-specialized.

As to the number of years working related to ICT, many of the ICT coordinators were into it with 2-5 years or a frequency of 10 (45.5%). Coming second is the group who worked 10 years and above with a frequency of 6 (27.3%). There is a diverse number as to the number of years the ICT coordinators have worked as to their positions since the inception of ICT in their respective schools depend on the time of implementation of the ICT program.

For the trainings, most of the respondents have attended trainings in the local, regional and national levels only. No one had the chance to attend international level. The number of times they had attended the trainings is also limited, usually four to six times. As implied, the ICT coordinators still need to be sent to trainings in order to equip or enhance their competence and capability in ICT.

ICT teachers. The profile of the ICT teachers includes the age, sex, civil status, highest educational attainment, specialization, number of years working related to ICT and seminars/trainings attended related to ICT. This is provided in Table 3.

Table 3 Profile of the Teachers

Age	f	%
60 and above (senior citizen)	0	0
46-59 (old age)	15	13.6
22-45 (middle-aged)	92	83.6
21 and below (young)	3	2.7
Total	110	100.00
Sex	f	%
Male	36	32.7
Female	74	67.3
Total	110	100.00

Civil Status	f	%
Single	35	31.8
Married	74	67.3
Widow/widower	1	0.9
Total	110	100.00
Highest Educational Attainment	f	%
Doctorate Degree Holder	2	1.8
Masters Degree with Doctoral Units	2	1.8
Masters Degree Holder	37	33.6
BS Degree with Masteral Units	24	21.6
BS Degree Holder	45	40.9
Total	110	100.00
Specialization	f	%
Educational Management	9	8.2
Mathematics	30	27.3
Science	11	10.0
Biological Science	4	3.6
Social Science	3	2.7
English	14	12.7
Araling Panlipunan	5	4.5
Filipino	2	1.8
MAPEH	5	4.5
TLE	17	15.5
Food Technology	3	2.7
Natural Science	3	2.7
Computer Hardware	2	1.8
Programming	1	0.9
Agriculture	1	0.9
Total	110	100.00
No. of Years working related to ICT	f	%
10 years and above	12	10.9
6 to 9 years	9	8.2
2 to 5 years	36	32.7
1 year and below	53	48.2
Total	110	100.00
Local Trainings	f	%
10 and above	1	0.9
7 -9 times	11	10.0
4-6 times	76	69.1
1-3 times	21	19.1
none	1	0.9
Total	110	100.00
Regional Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	2	1.8
4-6 times	1	0.9
1-3 times	15	13.6
none	92	83.6
Total	110	100.00
National Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0

7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	0	0
1-3 times	6	5.5
none	104	94.5
Total	110	100.00
International Trainings	f	%
10 and above	0	0
7 -9 times	0	0
4-6 times	1	0.9
1-3 times	1	0.9
none	108	98.2
Total	110	100.00

As illustrated in the above table, the biggest number of teachers which has a frequency of 92 (83.6%) are middle-age. Next is the group with a frequency of 15 (13.6%) at the age bracket 46-59 who are old age. The least is only 3 (2.7%) who belonged to the young age. With the given data, it simply tells that the younger teachers are more inclined to ICT and therefore they are more confident and capable in technology-related instructional delivery than the older ones.

For sex, female ICT teachers with a frequency of 74 (67.3%) dominated the male group with a frequency of 36 (32.7%). This turnout is unsurprising since both sexes are equally empowered when it comes to technology especially in today's generation.

In terms of civil status, married ICT teachers with a frequency of 74 (67.3%) prevailed over the single ones with a frequency of only 35 (31.8%). The given data simply imply that married teachers are many since they fall within the marrying age bracket.

When it comes to highest educational attainment, majority of the ICT teachers with a frequency of 45 (40.9%) were BS degree holders and this is closely followed by the group with master's degrees at a frequency of 37 (33.6%). The rest which is lesser in number had master's units and were doctoral degree holders. This just shows that the ICT teachers possess better educational qualifications and fit to the jobs they are assigned.

As to specialization, many of the teachers with a frequency of 30 (27.3%) specialized in Mathematics. Those who specialized in TLE with a frequency of 17 (15.5%) placed second and English majors came in third with a frequency of 14 (12.7%). The remaining groups were spread in different fields or disciplines which is less in number. Surprisingly, only one (0.9%) specialized in Programming. Specialization does not, after all, guarantee in the selection and designation of ICT teachers. This also implies that the Division utilizes certain criteria or system for assigning and designating ICT teachers.

As to the number of years working related to ICT, nearly half of the ICT teachers with a frequency of 53 (48.2%) had worked just a year. Meanwhile, there were those who had worked 2-5 years with a frequency of 36 (32.7%). The other portions less in number had worked 6-9 years and 10 years and more than. It can be inferred that the number of years the ICT teachers have worked for is dependent on the time when ICT was embraced or incepted in their school. Likewise, it implies that the earlier the ICT program was established in the school the longer the ICT teacher was assigned and had worked or served as well.

For the seminars/trainings attended, most of the ICT teachers had extensive exposures or experiences only in local and regional levels. Only few had attended in the national level while there was none in the international level. There is a great need to send more ICT teachers to training especially in the national and international levels. This means that the ICT teachers are not updated or lack the know-how as to the latest buzz in technology or ICT utilization.

Program Components

This section details the program components of the DepEd Computerization Program which covers integration of ICT in the school system and utilization of ICT resources. Data are presented in succeeding tables with corresponding discussions.

Table 4 Integration of ICT in School System by the School Administrators

Indicators	School Administrators	
	f	%
Applying ICT technology for online communication.	20	90.9
Facilitating the operationalization of the school management system like school information system, student tracking system and personnel information system using ICT.	20	90.9
Using ICT to access Teacher Support Materials (TSM), Learning Support Materials (LSM) and assessment tools in accordance with the guidelines.	22	100.0
Sharing with the other school heads the school's experience in the use of new technology.	11	50.0
Using ICT in establishing E-BEIS and baseline data of all performance indicator.	21	95.5
Using ICT in utilizing data like E-BEIS, SBM assessment, TSNA, and strategic planning in the development of SIP/AIP.	22	100.0
Managing curriculum innovation and enrichment with the use of technology.	15	68.2
Providing environment that promotes use of technology among learners and teachers	20	90.9
Assisting teachers in using technology to access, analyze, and interpret student performance data, and in using results to appropriately design, assess, and modify student instruction.	21	95.5
Designing, implementing, supporting, and participating collaboratively in professional development for all instructional staff that institutionalizes effective integration of technology for improved student learning.	13	59.1

*Multiple Responses

Integration of ICT in the school system. As provided in the table, integration of ICT in the school system was observed and is obviously high as most responses in the indicators usually more than fifty percent. For the administrators' case, using ICT to access Teacher Support Materials (TSM), Learning Support Materials (LSM) and assessment tools in accordance with the guidelines and using ICT in utilizing data like E-BEIS, SBM assessment, TSNA, and strategic planning in the development of SIP/AIP. were rated perfectly. The rest also obtained higher and favorable responses from the respondents except on the area: designing, implementing, supporting, and participating collaboratively in professional development for all instructional staff that institutionalizes effective integration of technology for improved student learning. From this response, it can be figured out, as perceived by the school administrators, that the ICT integration still has some gray areas and it's conspicuous that the implementers and beneficiaries still need upgrading of their ICT skills and competencies so that they will fully appreciate the usefulness as well as the impact of ICT towards education. Efforts of the schools or division pertaining to new or advanced methods in research which require the use of ICT should also be fostered.

Table 5 Integration of ICT in School System by ICT Coordinators and Teachers

Indicators	ICT Coordinators		Teachers	
	f	%	f	%
Designing, developing new or modifying existing digital/and or non-digital learning resources.	15	68.2	59	53.6
Planning and designing teaching-learning activities.	17	77.3	90	81.8
Processing assessment and evaluation data and report results.	17	71.3	80	72.7
Demonstrating proficiency in using computers to support teaching and learning	17	77.3	76	69.1
Using ICT tools and resources to improve efficiency and professional Practice	18	81.8	84	76.4
Practicing social responsibility, ethical and legal use of ICT tools and resources	14	63.6	62	56.4
Showing positive attitude towards the use of ICT in keeping records of the learners	20	90.9	90	81.8
Using ICT in students managing (Grading and attendance)	21	95.5	102	92.7
Using ICT in storing students' information (Student records, discipline, health systems)	20	90.9	86	78.2
Using ICT for communication and research	19	86.4	97	88.2

*Multiple Responses

On the part of the ICT coordinators, using ICT in managing students (grading and attendance), using ICT in storing students' information (Student records, discipline, health systems), and showing positive attitude towards the use of ICT keeping records of the learners gained higher ratings. Meanwhile, the lowest were "designing, developing new or modifying existing digital/and or non-digital learning experiences" and practicing social responsibility, ethical and legal use of ICT tools and resources.

From the perspective of the ICT coordinators, mentoring still needs to be enhanced to increase the knowledge and skills of the implementers and beneficiaries. Likewise, they too should be properly informed and oriented regarding sound, responsible and ethical usage of ICT.

On the other hand, the teachers highly rated “using ICT in managing students (grading and attendance), using ICT for communication and research and planning and designing teaching-learning activities. Designing, developing new or modifying existing digital/and or non-digital learning resources and practicing social responsibility, ethical and legal use of ICT tools and resources were perceived lowly. Just like the other sets of respondents, the teachers have also felt that ICT integration needs to be enhanced and implementers, beneficiaries and users should be properly informed as well as well-oriented about the legal issues that go with the use of ICT resources.

Table 6 Utilization of ICT Resources as Perceived by the ICT Coordinators

Subjects	No. of Hours every week	%
English	23	15.75
Filipino	20	13.70
Science	34	23.39
Mathematics	21	14.38
Aral. Pan./HEKASI	21	14.38
TLE-ICT	27	18.49
Total	146	100.0
Grade Level	No. of Hours every week	%
Grade 7	48	27.74
Grade 8	35	20.23
Grade 9	47	27.17
Fourth Year	43	26.86
Total	173	100.0

Utilization of ICT resources by the ICT coordinators. Table 7 reveals the utilization of ICT resources in all subject areas. The respondents found out that number of hours allotted every week is not equally distributed to the subjects. More hours were given to Science and TLE-ICT and the other subjects were nearly proportionate. The data shows that there was only average utilization of ICT in the subjects mentioned. The limited number of computer units due to damage and unserviceability and internet connection inaccessibility or problem have resulted to the limitation of the hours spent using ICT in classes.

Table 7 Utilization of ICT Resources as Perceived by the Teachers

Indicators	f	%
To prepare students for future jobs	55	50.0
To improve student achievement	86	78.2
To make learning more interesting	99	90.0
To develop student independence and responsibility for own learning	67	60.9
To promote active learning strategies	88	80.0
To encourage more cooperative and project-based learning	74	67.3
To individualize student learning experiences	66	60.0
To give students drill and practice exercises	78	70.9
To satisfy parents' and community expectations	58	52.7

To create and update lesson plans, exams and other teaching aids	105	95.5
To compute grades	109	99.1
To keep track of students' learning progress	100	90.9

Utilization of ICT resources as perceived by the teachers. As presented in the table, the purposes and reasons why ICT resources should be utilized were noted by the teachers. Yielding the most number of responses is “to compute grades”; followed by “to create and update lesson plans, exams and other teaching aids; another is “to keep track of students’ learning progress and “to make learning more interesting”. From the given responses, it can be implied that the teachers find ICT resources more valuable and helpful in making their task easier and quicker especially when it comes to computation of grades and in facilitating other reports and teaching-related activities. Moreover, it also paves the way to a slick and streaming lesson presentations which further motivate and encourage the learners to be interactive and make learning more fun and highly interesting.

Strategies Employed in the DCP Implementation

The implementation of the program has also certain strategies. Utilization of such strategies was determined as to its frequency through the three sets of respondents as provided in the subsequent tables below.

Table 8 Strategies Employed in the DCP Implementation As Perceived by the School Administrators

Indicators	WM	Description
The DCP recipient schools were oriented on the counterpart requirements needed before the delivery of the computer package.	4.64	Always utilized
The school head, ICT coordinator and property custodian were oriented on the inspection and acceptance of the computer packages.	4.68	Always utilized
The school head, ICT coordinator and property custodian were trained/oriented to enhanced their skills for instructional purposes and effective governance through an ICT-aided environment, for example the use of LRMS Portal, inter-active learning materials, etc.	4.45	Often utilized
The school head was oriented to develop their ICT leadership.	4.36	Often utilized
The school head, ICT coordinator and Property Custodian were oriented to familiarize them the existing DepEd ICT Systems.	4.41	Often utilized
The school was assessed and validated as to the compliance of the school counterpart requirements.	4.54	Always utilized
The school head was assisted in preparing the school to be ready for the delivery of the computers.	4.50	Always utilized
The school was supervised and coordinated for the delivery of computers to the school.	4.50	Always utilized
The school was monitored on the utilization of the computers to the school.	4.0	Often utilized
The school submitted reports on the implementation of the program (school readiness checklist, DCP Deployment process, etc.).	4.04	Often utilized
AWM	4.41	Often utilized

Strategies employed in the DCP implementation as perceived by the school administrators. As reported in the table, the strategies employed in the program were utilized most of the time. The school head, ICT coordinator and property custodian were oriented on the inspection and acceptance of the computer packages were finally handed to the

recipients. The DCP recipient schools were oriented on the counterpart requirements needed before the delivery of the computer package were also done. All of the strategies were carefully observed which means that the school recipients conformed to the strategies required in the implementation of the program.

Table 9 Strategies Employed in the DCP Implementation As Perceived by the ICT Coordinators

Indicators	WM	Description
The ICT coordinator was oriented on the counterpart requirements needed before the delivery of the computer package.	4.54	Always utilized
The ICT coordinator was oriented on the inspection and acceptance of the computer package.	4.64	Always utilized
The ICT coordinator was trained/oriented to enhance his skills for instructional purposes and effective governance through an ICT-aided environment, for example the use of LRMDs Portal, inter-active learning materials, etc.	4.5	Always utilized
The ICT coordinator was oriented to familiarize him on the existing DepEd ICT system.	4.27	Often utilized
The e-classroom was assessed and validated as to the compliance of the school counterpart requirements.	4.68	Always utilized
The ICT coordinator was assisted in preparing the school to be ready for the delivery of the computers.	4.68	Always utilized
The ICT coordinator was informed on the schedule of e-classroom package delivery to the school?	4.41	Often utilized
The ICT coordinator was trained on how to manage ICT facilities.	4.45	Often utilized
The school submitted reports on the implementation of the program (school readiness checklist, DCP Deployment process, etc.).	3.86	Often utilized
The school was monitored on the utilization of the computers.	3.45	Frequent utilized
AWM	4.35	Often utilized

Strategies employed in the DCP implementation as perceived by the ICT coordinators. As illustrated in the table, the strategies in the DCP implementation were indeed followed as perceived by the ICT coordinators through the Average Weighted Mean of 4.35 interpreted as often utilized. The ICT coordinators perceived that strategies were properly followed prior and after implementation of the program. This implies that the school recipients conformed to appropriate steps and procedures as reflective of the utilization of prescribed strategies.

Table 10 Strategies Employed in the DCP Implementation As Perceived by the Teachers

Indicators	WM	Description
The ICT coordinator was oriented on the counterpart requirements needed before the delivery of the computer package.	4.29	Often utilized
The ICT coordinator was oriented on the inspection and acceptance of the computer package.	4.40	Often utilized
The ICT coordinator was trained/oriented to enhance his skills for instructional purposes and effective governance through an ICT-aided environment, for example the use of LRMDs Portal, inter-active learning materials, etc.	4.45	Often utilized
The ICT coordinator was oriented to familiarize him on the existing DepEd ICT system.	4.39	Often utilized

The e-classroom was assessed and validated as to the compliance of the school counterpart requirements.	4.23	Often utilized
The ICT coordinator was assisted in preparing the school to be ready for the delivery of the computers.	4.29	Often utilized
The ICT coordinator was informed on the schedule of e-classroom package delivery to the school?	3.97	Often utilized
The ICT coordinator was trained on how to manage ICT facilities.	3.58	Often utilized
The school submitted reports on the implementation of the program (school readiness checklist, DCP Deployment process, etc.).	4.41	Often utilized
The school was monitored on the utilization of the computers.	4.31	Often utilized
AWM	4.23	Often utilized

Strategies employed in the DCP implementation as perceived by the teachers. As reflected in the table, the strategies employed in the DCP implementation were utilized often as perceived by the teachers through the Average Weighted Mean of 4.23 interpreted as often utilized. This goes to show that proper procedures and processes prescribed in the implementation of the program were practiced by the school recipients.

Level of Implementation of the DepEd Computerization Program

This part showcases the level of implementation of the DCP as perceived by the three sets of respondents: school administrators, ICT coordinators and teachers. Tables below are supplemented with full details of the discussions.

Table 11 Level of Implementation of the DCP as Perceived by the School Administrators

Indicators	WM	Description
The school was informed as recipient of DepEd Computerization Program (DCP).	4.64	Very highly implemented
The school head and ict coordinator were oriented on the DCP Deployment.	4.68	Very highly implemented
The school head and ict coordinator were provided with the technical assistance in preparing the e-classroom for the delivery of the computers.	4.36	Highly implemented
The e-classroom was assessed and validated as to the compliance of the school counterpart requirements.	4.45	Highly implemented
The school submitted accomplished school readiness checklist.	4.54	Very highly implemented
Details of the delivery of computers to the school was coordinated by the division ict coordinator or the supplier.	4.5	Highly implemented
The school inspectorate team inspected the ICT facilities in accordance to its technical specifications.	4.45	Highly implemented
The teachers undergo hands on training on the utilization of e-classroom.	4.04	Highly implemented
The school submitted reports to the division ICT coordinator on the implementation of the DCP program (e.g. DCP Deployment processes data, etc.)	4.14	Highly implemented
The school integrated ICT in the school system.	4.09	Moderately implemented
The school was monitored and evaluated on the utilization of e-classroom	3.63	
AWM	4.32	Highly implemented

Level of implementation of the DCP as perceived by the school administrators. As viewed from the table, there were eleven activities conducted in the implementation of the program. From the results, it was found out as perceived by the school administrators that the level of implementation is high as evident of the Average Weighted Mean of 4.32 interpreted as highly implemented. Among the activities, only in “The school was monitored and evaluated on the utilization of the e-classroom” is a little low compared to the rest of the activities. This would imply that integration of ICT in the school system has to be reinforced, making implementation of this activity quite high.

Table 12 Level of Implementation of the DCP as Perceived by the ICT Coordinators

Indicators	WM	Description
The school was informed as recipient of DepEd Computerization Program (DCP).	4.59	Very highly implemented
The school head and ict coordinator were oriented on the DCP Deployment.	4.27	Highly implemented
The school head and ict coordinator were provided with the technical assistance in preparing the e-classroom for the delivery of the computers.	4.18	Highly implemented
The e-classroom was assessed and validated as to the compliance of the school counterpart requirements.	4.32	Highly implemented
The school submitted accomplished school readiness checklist.	4.27	Highly implemented
Details of the delivery of computers to the school was coordinated by the division ict coordinator or the supplier.	4.14	Highly implemented
The school inspectorate team inspected the ICT facilities in accordance to its technical specifications.	4.27	Highly implemented
The teachers undergo hands on training on the utilization of e-classroom.	4.00	Highly implemented
The school submitted reports to the division ICT coordinator on the implementation of the DCP program (e.g. DCP Deployment processes data, etc.)	4.09	Highly implemented
The school integrated ICT in the school system.	3.72	Highly implemented
The school was monitored and evaluated on the utilization of e-classroom	3.14	Moderately implemented
AWM	4.09	Highly implemented

Level of implementation of the DCP as perceived by the ICT coordinators. As gleaned from the table, there were eleven activities conducted in the implementation of the program. From the results, it was found out as perceived by the ICT coordinators that the level of implementation is high as evident of the Average Weighted Mean of 4.09 interpreted as highly implemented. However, among the activities, only in “The school was monitored and evaluated on the utilization of e-classroom” that the ICT coordinators rated it moderately implemented. This means that monitoring and evaluation on utilization of the e-classroom needs to be improved, thereby making the implementation of this activity highly implemented.

Table 13 Level of Implementation of the DCP as Perceived by the Teachers

Indicators	WM	Description
The school was informed as recipient of DepEd Computerization Program (DCP).	4.15	Highly implemented
The school head and ict coordinator were oriented on the DCP Deployment.	4.30	Highly implemented

The school head and ict coordinator were provided with the technical assistance in preparing the e-classroom for the delivery of the computers.	4.27	Highly implemented
The e-classroom was assessed and validated as to the compliance of the school counterpart requirements.	4.27	Highly implemented
The school submitted accomplished school readiness checklist.	4.16	Highly implemented
Details of the delivery of computers to the school was coordinated by the division ICT coordinator or the supplier.	3.95	Highly implemented
The school inspectorate team inspected the ICT facilities in accordance to its technical specifications.	4.03	Highly implemented
The teachers undergo hands on training on the utilization of e-classroom.	3.89	Highly implemented
The school submitted reports to the division ICT coordinator on the implementation of the DCP program (e.g. DCP Deployment processes data, etc.)	3.56	Moderately implemented
The school integrated ICT in the school system.	3.89	Highly implemented
The school was monitored and evaluated on the utilization of e-classroom	3.56	Moderately implemented
AWM	4.00	Highly implemented

Level of implementation of the DCP as perceived by the teachers. From the given table, there were eleven activities conducted in the implementation of the program. It was found out as perceived by the teachers that the level of implementation of the program is very high as evident in the Average Weighted Mean of 4.00 interpreted as highly implemented. However, among the activities, only two “The school was monitored and evaluated on the utilization of e-classroom” and “The school submitted reports to the division ICT coordinator on the implementation of the DCP program (e.g. DCP Deployment processes data, etc.)” that the teachers rated moderately implemented. It can be inferred that the school-recipient have to intensify monitoring and evaluation on utilization of the e-classroom and the submission of reports to the division ICT coordinator regarding the implementation program as these are somewhat average in level.

Relationship of Variables

The significant relationships between the variables considered were determined through the aid of the Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS). Data are presented in the succeeding tables.

Table 14 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the School Administrators and the Integration of ICT in the School System

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	4.917	5	.161	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	4.444	5	.487	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	10.000	15	.820	Ho Accepted
Specialization	16.528	20	.683	Ho Accepted
trainings	5.333	5	.377	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision	
Age	-.574	.083	Ho Accepted	

As revealed in Table 14, the profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the school administrators obtained chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. From these results, it is evident that the hypothesis that says “there is no significant

relationship between the profile of the school administrators and the integration of ICT in the school system was accepted and therefore not significant. Implication can be drawn that sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the school administrators are not directly related or affected by ICT integration. This further means that the school administrators possess welcoming and positive impression towards ICT.

Table 15 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the School Administrators and the Strategies Employed by the DepEd

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	10.000	8	.265	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	10.000	8	.265	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	30.000	24	.185	Ho Accepted
Specialization	40.000	32	.157	Ho Accepted
trainings	14.286	16	.557	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	.174	.630		Ho Accepted

It can be gleaned from Table 15 that the profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the school administrators obtained chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. From these results, it is evident that the hypothesis that says “there is no significant relationship between the profile of the school administrators and the strategies employed by DepEd was accepted and therefore not significant. Implication can be drawn that sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the school administrators are not directly related or affected by the strategies employed by DepEd. This would also imply that the strategies of the DCP are both accepted and favoured by the school administrators.

Table 16 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the School Administrators and the Level of Implementation of the DCP

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	8.839	9	.452	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	11.000	9	.276	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	44.000	36	.169	Ho Accepted
Specialization	41.067	36	.169	Ho Accepted
trainings	15.813	18	.606	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	.285	.396		Ho Accepted

Table 16 indicates the profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the school administrators which obtained chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. From these results, it is evident that the hypothesis that says “there is no significant relationship between the profile of the school administrators and the level of implementation of the DCP was accepted and therefore not significant. This only means that sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the school administrators are not directly related or affected by the level of implementation of the DCP. Likewise, this could also imply that the school administrators are supportive in the implementation of the program.

Table 17 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the ICT Coordinators and the Integration of ICT in the School System

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	12.500	12	.406	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	5.833	6	.442	Ho Accepted

Educational Attainment	17.000	12	.150	Ho Accepted
Specialization	41.667	36	.238	Ho Accepted
Trainings	14.167	12	.290	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	-.343	.331		Ho Accepted
Number of years	-.174	.630		Ho Accepted

As provided in Table 17 the profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years in service of the school administrators which obtained chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. The findings mainly advance that hypothesis “there is no significant relationship between the profile of the ICT administrators and the integration of the ICT in the school system was accepted and therefore not significant. This only means that sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years in service of the school administrators are not directly related or affected by the integration of ICT in the school system. Moreover, this may imply that the ICT coordinators.

Table 18 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the ICT Coordinators and the Utilization of ICT Resources

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	14.375	16	.571	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	10.000	8	.265	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	13.750	16	.617	Ho Accepted
Specialization	50.000	48	.394	Ho Accepted
Trainings	20.000	16	.220	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	-.510	.132		Ho Accepted
Number of years	-.432	.212		Ho Accepted

Shown in Table 18 are the data on the relationship between the profile of the ICT coordinators and the utilization of ICT resources. The profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years garnered chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. Such results propose that the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the ICT coordinators and the utilization of ICT resources was accepted and therefore not significant. It can be inferred from the findings that the ICT coordinators’ sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years in service did not have any bearing or relationship as to utilization of ICT resources.

Table 19 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the ICT Coordinators and the Strategies Employed by the DepEd

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	20.000	16	.220	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	10.000	8	.265	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	14.000	16	.599	Ho Accepted
Specialization	52.500	48	.304	Ho Accepted
Trainings	14.167	16	.586	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	-.055	.881		Ho Accepted
Number of years	.291	.415		Ho Accepted

Table 19 indicates data on the relationship between the profile of the ICT coordinators and the strategies employed by DepEd. The profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number

of years posted chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at $\alpha=0.05$. The results mainly report the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the ICT coordinators and the utilization of ICT resources was accepted and therefore not significant. It can be inferred from the findings that the ICT coordinators' sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years in service did not have any bearing or relationship as to the strategies employed by DepEd.

Table 20 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the ICT Coordinators and the Level of Implementation of the DCP

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	22.000	16	.143	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	11.000	8	.202	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	13.200	16	.658	Ho Accepted
Specialization	51.333	48	.344	Ho Accepted
Trainings	18.333	16	.305	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	-.156	.646		Ho Accepted
Number of years	.120	.726		Ho Accepted

Highlighted in Table 20 are the data on the relationship between the profile of the ICT coordinators and the level of implementation of the DCP. The profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years garnered chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at $\alpha=0.05$. Such results propose that the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the ICT coordinators and the level of implementation of the DCP was accepted and therefore not significant. It can be inferred from the findings that the ICT coordinators' sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years in service did not have any bearing or relationship as to the level of implementation of the DCP.

Table 21 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Teachers and the Integration of ICT in the School System

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	7.917	8	.442	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	7.917	8	.442	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	17.750	16	.339	Ho Accepted
Specialization	62.500	58	.256	Ho Accepted
Trainings	30.000	24	.185	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	-.086	.813		Ho Accepted
Number of years	.034	.925		Ho Accepted

Presented in Table 21 are the data on relationship between the profile of the teachers and the integration of ICT in the school system. The profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the teachers tallied chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at $\alpha=0.05$. From these results, it is evident that the hypothesis that says "there is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the integration of ICT in the school system was accepted and therefore not significant. Implication can be drawn that sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the teachers are not directly related or affected by ICT integration. This further means that the teachers are positive about ICT integration.

Table 22 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Teachers and the Utilization of ICT Resources

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	12.000	11	.364	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	12.000	11	.364	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	24.000	22	.347	Ho Accepted
Specialization	84.000	77	.274	Ho Accepted
Trainings	36.000	33	.330	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	.409	.187		Ho Accepted
Number of years	.263	.408		Ho Accepted

Table 22 encompasses data on the relationship between the profile of the teachers and the utilization of ICT resources. The profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years garnered chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. Such results propose that the hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the utilization of ICT resources was accepted and therefore not significant. It can be inferred from the findings that the teachers' sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings, age and number of years in service did not have any bearing or relationship as to utilization of ICT resources.

Table 23 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Teachers and the Strategies Employed by the DepEd

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	7.917	8	.442	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	10.000	8	.265	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	14.000	16	.599	Ho Accepted
Specialization	60.000	56	.333	Ho Accepted
Trainings	24.286	24	.445	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	-.235	.574		Ho Accepted
Number of years	.299	.401		Ho Accepted

Table 23 showcases the significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the strategies employed by DepEd. The teachers' profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the school administrators obtained chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. From these results, it is evident that the hypothesis that says "there is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the strategies employed by DepEd was accepted and therefore not significant. Implication can be drawn that sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the teachers are not directly related or affected by the strategies employed by DepEd. This would also imply that the strategies of the DCP are both accepted and favoured by the teachers.

Table 24 Significant Relationship between the Profile of the Teachers and the Level of Implementation of the DCP

Variable	X ²	df	p-value	Decision
sex	6.679	7	.463	Ho Accepted
Civil Status	6.679	7	.463	Ho Accepted
Educational Attainment	19.800	14	.137	Ho Accepted
Specialization	63.250	49	.083	Ho Accepted
Trainings	20.625	21	.482	Ho Accepted
Variable	r-value	Sig.(2-tailed)		Decision
Age	.556	.076		Ho Accepted
Number of years	-.103	.762		Ho Accepted

Table 24 showcases the profile variables on sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the teachers which obtained chi-square and p-values and r-values greater than the actual values with corresponding df at alpha=0.05. From these results, it is evident that the hypothesis that says “there is no significant relationship between the profile of the teachers and the level of implementation of the DCP was accepted and therefore not significant. This only means that sex, civil status, educational attainment, specialization, trainings and age of the teachers are not directly related or affected by the level of implementation of the DCP. Likewise, this could also imply that the teachers are supportive in the implementation of the program.

Table 25 Significant Difference in Perceived Implementation of the DCP between School Administrators, ICT Coordinators and Teachers

Variables	r	Sig.(2-tailed)	Decision
School Administrators and ICT Coordinators	.913**	.000	Ho Rejected
School Administrators and Teachers	.808**	.003	Ho Rejected
ICT Coordinators and Teachers	.709**	.015	Ho Rejected

Described in Table 25 is the significant difference in perceived implementation of the DCP between the school administrators, ICT coordinators and teachers.

Using the t-test, it can be figured out in the table that the variables tested posted mean scores statistically similar to each other which implies that the school administrators, ICT coordinators and teachers did have related or parallel perceptions of the Computerization Program implementation. This only marks the consistent as well as collective beliefs of the school administrators, ICT coordinators and teachers on the importance, relevance and value that ICT can enormously contribute in the upkeep of the schools towards quality education

CONCLUSIONS

Primarily, the profile of the DepEd Computerization Program is a major asset which became the core strength in its implementation since the respondents possessed the qualifications needed for them to implement, manage and operationalize the program, although in some aspects deficiencies were still present.

The program components were on the average in terms of utilization as well as implementation. Conspicuously, it was implemented partially in that sense.

Utilization of ICT resources is not equitable and it requires procedural and workable measures to improve implementation. Interestingly, monitoring and evaluation is carefully observed and therefore highly implemented. This should be sustained so utilization would be fully integrated in the education system.

Some of the strategies were highly implemented and only in few areas that implementation was in the average level.

The perceptions of the school administrators, ICT coordinators and teachers regarding the implementation of the program were in unison and that the implementation is still partial and in the average level.

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